

Creativity and Innovation in Teaching and Learning

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Abstract

Creativity and Innovation are important things in teaching and learning. Main aim of teaching is to bring about socially desirable behavioural changes in the students. JohnDewey says that Education is Life, life is education. The types of education is formal, informal, non formal. In this paper, we are focus on new tools and technology which help us to understand creativity and innovation in teaching and learning. Creativity is the interaction between the learning environment both teachers and students. It's a clear problem-solving process. When try something new, there is an element of creativity involved. Innovation in education encourages students and teachers. Innovation in education comes in many forms. Pedagogy is going with continuous innovation. Technology assets teachers in providing a more effective learning experience for the students. Schools with all infrastructure like computers, LCD projectors, white board, internet, webcam, printers, scanner, LAN and WAN, called as smart school. Therefore, innovation with modern technology should be involved in education and learning system, so that each one will be updated.

Keywords Teacher, Student, Creativity, Innovation, Learning, Teaching, New, Education, Technology, Skill, Experience, Thinking, Values.

Introduction

Today with advantages of modern teaching methods of teaching have been introduced. It's an education reform which provides an entirely different angle of teaching and learning. In traditional teaching methods teachers still use a conventional chalk-talk method in the classroom to teach students who can provide only basic knowledge of all subjects, but now teachers adapt new tools, innovations and creativity in teaching methods is learner centred. With various dramatic scientific and technological advances such as the rise of big data, machine and artificial intelligence. Education thus must move towards less content and more towards learning about how to think critically and solve problems, how to be creative and multidisciplinary and how to innovate, adapt and absorb new material in novel and changing fields, pedagogy must evolve to make Education more experiential, holistic, integrated, inquiry-driven, discovery-oriented, learner centred, discussion based, flexible, and of course enjoyable. The curriculum must include basic, arts, humanities, games, sports and fitness, languages, literature,culture and values in all subjects.

Aim of study

Main Aim of the presented Research Paper : Introduction of Technology and Innovation to develop Creativity in Teaching and learning between Teacher and Students.

Review of Literature

Anna Craft explained in the the book 'Creativity in Schools' (2005), creativity in schools is changing, with greater emphasis on curriculum and relationships of students and teachers.

Strengthening education system and innovation, by Unicef, Innovation in education is about more than new technology. Its about solving a real problem and improve teaching learning process.

A list of Information communication tools for teaching and learning, covering everything from digital infrastructure and replacing physical classes by online live./ recorded sessions.

Main Text**Creativity and Innovation in education system**

Education refers to the process of acquiring knowledge, skills, values and self-directed learning and experiential learning. Education helps individuals to develop their intellectual, emotional, social and physical abilities, enabling them to achieve personal and professional success and contribute to society. Education also plays a critical role in promoting economic growth, social mobility and cultural development. Education rapidly changing world and to become responsible.

Education system proposed by Mahatma Gandhi is called as "basic education". He mainly aims at the education in mother tongue and asked for activity and creativity centred education to make the children skilled and independent.

Education like family, marriage, religion, law and politics is one of the important institutions of society which plays a role in maintaining and developing social system (Tandan,2016). John Dewey says about the education that "Education is life, life is education".

Teachers were the only means to create a bridge between teaching and learning. They were using conventional pedagogical methods to explain the topic or to provide notes. Now in recent years, Creativity and Innovation are essential components of effective teaching and learning. Creativity is the interaction between the teachers and students and a clear problem-solving process. Teachers can develop these qualities-

Art's subjects such as art and design music, drama and dance are often associated with creativity and innovation. Learner often works on projects that they have devised themselves, according to their own interests and passion. Original work is particularly valued in both informal and formal assessments. When learners take control of their work in this way, their levels of internal motivation tend to increase (craft,2005).Teacher to connect with others in your field members, attend talks and workshop live or online and sharing your knowledge with your students. Then learners respond positively to teachers, who don't follow the same old steps in the same old way day in and day out.

New tools and technologies in teaching and learning

Innovation in education comes in many forms. Pedagogy is going with continuous innovation. In the 1990, there are a variety of schools that have computer-based learning system and today emergence of multiple media technologies give a new impulse to situated learning theories favouring learning in context scenarios. A school with all infrastructure like computer, LCD projectors, Interactive, white board, Internet, webcam, printers, scanner, LAN and WAN called as smart school. There are various types of tools and technologies used in classroom. Here are some ways of creativity and innovation that can be corporate into teaching and learning:

1. Project based learning: Project based learning is an innovative teaching method that allows students to work on projects that interest them while still learning the necessary skills and knowledge. This approach encourages creativity, problem-solving and critical thinking skills.
2. Flipped classroom: The flipped classroom is flipping the traditional classroom model. In this approach students learn new concepts and material outside of class and then come to class to work on projects and engage in discussions.
3. Game based learning: Uses games and simulation to teach new concepts and skills. This approach can develop collaboration skills.
4. Creativity and assessments: This can help students to demonstrate their understanding of new concepts and material in innovative ways. This can include things like creating videos, writing a blog post or designing a website.
5. Virtual and Augmented Reality: Virtual and Augmented reality technology has been used to create immersive learning experiences that can help students to better understand complex concepts.
6. Adaptive learning: Adaptive learning technology uses algorithms and artificial intelligence to tailor instruction to unique needs and learning style of each student.
7. Online Classroom platforms: Online learning platforms are becoming increasingly popular. These platforms offer students the flexibility to learn at their own pace, from anywhere in the world.
8. Micro learning: Micro learning involves breaking down larger learning objectives into smaller, more manageable pieces
9. Computer in the classroom- Teacher are able to demonstrate a new lesson and show new information on websites.
10. Wireless classroom microphones- With the help of microphones, students are able to hear their teachers more clearly.

11. Mobile devices- Mobile devices such as tablet or smartphone can be used to enhance the experience in the classroom.
12. Interactive whiteboard: - It provides touch controls of computer applications
13. Online study tools- Tools that motivate student to studying by making more fun.
14. Spaced learning- This is being followed by teachers. In this method teachers repeat a lesson multiple times, basically unit the students understanding entirely. However, the teacher repeats the course with two 10-minute spaces (break) in between the lessons.
15. Learning management system (LMS)- LMS platforms such as canvas, Moodle and blackboard provide a central location for teachers to deliver course, content, communicate with students and manage grades and assignments.
16. VAC teaching- VAC is modern teaching method whose effects can be seen clearly. InVAC, V is visual means seeing the data, A is audio means gathering information by hearing the data and K is kinaesthetic means feeling the data. A teacher should keep the category of students in kind while teaching because some students catch the information by seeing, by hearing or by feeling so they should present the same material in different ways.

Conclusion

Overall creativity and innovation can help to make teaching and learning more engaging effective and enjoyable by incorporating these technologies and teaching methods into the classroom, teachers can provide students with innovative learning experiences that help to achieve their academic goals. These concepts into the classroom, teachers can help students to develop critical thinking skills, problem-solving, and a love of learning that will last a lifetime. Teachers are introducing different innovative ideas to explain the content to learners. Also, it is the responsibility of teachers to teach students with suitable and modern technology, tools and methods. It is a teacher's success. So, it becomes the duty of a teacher to take a step towards accepting modern technology, tools and methods of teaching. To provide a sound education, there should be an amalgamation of a skilled teacher and innovative ways of teaching. So that students will be ready with not only theoretical knowledge but also with practical experience of subjects to face the world and compete against their competitors.

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